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ORIGINALNI RADOVI

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PERIOPERATIVNA NUTRITIVNA TERAPIJA KOD PACIJENATA SA INFLAMATORNIM BOLESTIMA CREVA – SKRINING, DIJAGNOSTIKA I TERAPIJA PERIOPERATIVNE MALNUTRICIJE

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SAŽETAK

Uvod: Inflammatorne bolesti creva (IBC) predstavljaju grupu crevnih poremećaja koji dovode do hronične inflamacije gastrointestinalnog trakta. IBC obuhvataju Kronovu bolest i ulcerozni kolitis. Uprkos napretku nehirurškog lečenja, poput biološke, antibiotske i nutritivne terapije, ovi pacijenti zahtevaju hirurški tretman. Dokazano je da je malnutricija glavni faktor rizika za perioperativne komplikacije.

Cilj: uočavanje najvećih izazova u perioperativnom periodu kod pacijenata sa inflamatornim bolestima creva.

Materijal i metode: istraživanje je sprovedeno popunjavanjem anonimnog onlajn upitnika koji se sastoji od dvadeset četiri pitanja. Upitnik je distribuiran onlajn, ciljajući anesteziologe, gastroenterologe i hirurge. Statistička analiza je izvršena korišćenjem SPSS 21.0.

Rezultati: Anesteziolozi su činili 72,9% ispitanika, 20,3% hirurzi i 6,8% gastroenterolozi. Svega 8,6% specijalista redovno koristi alate za skrining malnutricije, dok 12,1% ispitanika obavlja redovnu nutritivnu podršku za pacijente sa IBD. Najčešći alati za procenu nutritivnog statusa su anamneza, fizikalni pregledi, antropometrijska merenja i laboratorijski testovi. U preoperativnom periodu 90,1% nutritivne podrške čini kombinacija enteralne i parenteralne ishrane. Svi ispitanici su se složili da su glavni izazovi u radu nedostatak edukacije, organizacione podrške, vremena i resursa.

Zaključak: Preoperativna nutritivna procena i terapija kod bolesnika sa IBC se još uvek ne koriste rutinski, a metode i vreme trajanja su još uvek različite. Dalji rad na edukaciji, implementaciji i identifikaciji u pravcu nutritivne podrške kod ovih pacijenata je od vitalnog značaja

Ključne reči: inflamatorne bolesti creva, malnutricija, perioperativni period

SUMMARY

Introduction: Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) encompasses a group of intestinal disorders characterized by chronic inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract. IBD includes Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis. Despite advances in non-surgical management, including biologics, antibiotics, and nutritional support, patients with IBD commonly require surgical treatment. Malnutrition is found to be a significant risk factor for postoperative complications.

Objective: This review will focus on the role of healthcare professionals in preoperative assessment, the challenges in perioperative care, and management principles for patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).

Methods: This research was conducted by filling out an anonymous online questionnaire consisting of twenty-four questions. The questionnaire was distributed online, targeting doctors, specialists in anesthesiology, gastroenterology, and surgery. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 21.0.

Results: The study involved 59 healthcare professionals specializing in different fields. 72.9% of them were anesthesiologists, 20.3% were surgeons, and 6.8% were gastroenterologists. Only 8.6% of specialists use the Malnutrition Screening Tool regularly. Only 12.1% of respondents are performing regular Nutritional support for patients with IBD. The most commonly used tools for nutritional assessment include anamnesis and physical examinations, anthropometric measurements, and laboratory tests. In the preoperative period, 90.1% of nutritional support is a combination of enteral and parenteral nutrition. All of the respondents agreed that the main challenges are a lack of knowledge, organizational support, time, and resources.

Conclusion: No specific preoperative nutritional support is regularly used, and methods and timing remain diverse. Further work on education, implementation, and identifying clinical needs and benefits for nutritional support in patients is vitally needed.

Keywords: Inflammatory bowel disease, malnutrition, perioperative period

Introduction

Inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD), which include Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis, are marked by chronic and recurring inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract [1]. The clinical progression of these diseases can vary significantly, but it is most often characterized by periods of activity and remission [2]. Part of their complexity is centered on the fact that, although they originate from the gastrointestinal tract, these diseases often manifest clinically in other organ systems, such as the spine, eyes, and skin, which can worsen systemic inflammation and additionally require immunosuppressive therapy. Chronic inflammation and immunosuppressive therapy hurt the ability of these patients to feed themselves [3]. Although we have seen daily progress in new non-surgical therapeutic methods that have reduced the rate of hospital admission for these patients, the rate of indication for operative care remains high. The course of these diseases is progressive and often requires surgery to remove certain parts of the gastrointestinal tract, whether due to severe colitis, perforation, fistulas, dysplasia, or malignant changes. Certain studies estimate that 26-47% of patients with Crohn's disease will require operative management ten years after diagnosis, and more than 80% twenty years after diagnosis [4, 5].

Malnutrition is a significant independent risk factor for patients with IBDs, affecting up to 70% of this population. Patients who are malnourished and undergo surgical treatment face a particularly high risk of postoperative complications. Malnutrition can lead to delayed recovery from illness and surgery, as well as impaired wound healing, which often results in more extended hospital stays and increased hospital costs [6, 7]. Several factors contribute to the decline in nutritional status among these patients, including reduced food intake, increased gastrointestinal tract losses, nutrient malabsorption, heightened dietary needs due to systemic inflammation, and iatrogenic factors [8, 9]. Since malnutrition is a modifiable risk factor, it's crucial to understand how preoperative assessments of nutritional status can impact surgical

outcomes. This understanding highlights the importance of administering perioperative dietary therapy for patients with IBD [10, 11].

The European Society for Clinical Nutrition and Metabolism (ESPEN) recommends that patients be screened for malnutrition at the time of diagnosis, with regular follow-up assessments thereafter [12]. While these patients may appear well-nourished, they are often at risk for micronutrient deficiencies, particularly in vitamin D, zinc, iron, vitamin B6, vitamin B12, and vitamin C. Therefore, it is essential to screen for and address these deficiencies [13]. Diagnosing malnutrition can be challenging, especially in patients with IBD, and no gold standard for diagnosis has been established yet [14]. Standard clinical tools for assessing nutritional status include body mass index (BMI), unintentional weight loss, reduced intake of essential micro- and macronutrients, and the percentage of body fat [13].

Recent recommendations suggest that specific indicators are crucial for identifying severe malnutrition, particularly in patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). These indicators include a weight loss of more than 10–15% within six months, a body mass index (BMI) of less than 18.5 kg/m², and serum albumin levels below 30 g/L [10, 12, 15]. According to the ESPEN guidelines, patients with IBD should be screened for malnutrition using validated nutritional screening tools, similar to protocols for patients undergoing general surgery [16]. The Nutritional Risk Score 2002 (NRS 2002) and the Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool (MUST) are specifically recommended for this purpose [16, 17]. A score of 3 or higher is associated with an increased risk of gastrointestinal surgery and indicates the need for nutritional support [18]. Additionally, other universal nutritional screening tools that may be utilized include the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA), the Subjective Global Assessment scale (SGA), the Nutritional Risk Index (NRI), and the Controlling Nutritional Status score (CONUT) [19, 20]. When considering ESPEN recommendations for nutritional support in these patients, energy deli-

very should be set at 30–35 kcal/kg/day, as the energy requirements for individuals with IBD are comparable to those of the healthy population. If there is a clinical suspicion of varying energy needs in specific disease states, individual energy requirements should be assessed using indirect calorimetry along with a personalized physical activity factor. Individuals with active IBD have increased protein requirements, which should be raised to 1.2–1.5 g/kg/d for adults compared to general population recommendations. Every patient with IBD deserves the benefit of personalized counseling from a skilled dietitian [12]. This is an integral part of a comprehensive multidisciplinary approach, not only enriching nutritional therapy but also playing a vital role in safeguarding against malnutrition and related disorders. Prioritizing this support can significantly improve health outcomes and enhance overall well-being. Determining the best approach to medical nutrition in IBD can be complex and depends on several factors. These include the patient's ability to eat, the absorptive capacity of the gastrointestinal tract, the patient's nutritional and inflammatory status, and the therapeutic goals. Oral nutritional supplements are typically the first step and are considered a supportive therapy that complements a regular diet. When possible, enteral nutrition (EN) should be prioritized over parenteral nutrition (PN). However, if EN does not meet more than 60% of a patient's energy needs, it should be supplemented with parenteral nutrition (PN), particularly during the perioperative period [12, 21, 22].

Optimizing the preoperative nutritional status in patients with IBD through a collaborative approach among healthcare specialists is essential for achieving favorable surgical outcomes.

Objective

This review aims to highlight the importance of preoperative nutritional therapy and the involvement of various healthcare professionals in clinical practice during preoperative assessments, addressing challenges in perioperative care, and outlining management principles for

patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).

Methods

This study employed an online questionnaire comprising twenty-four questions, designed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of various medical professionals regarding nutritional support for patients with inflammatory bowel disease. The questionnaire was distributed online through professional associations, targeting doctors who specialize in anesthesiology, surgery, and gastroenterology, who are involved in patient care and nutritional assessment. It's important to note that the study's focus on nutritional support for inflammatory bowel disease is directly relevant to your field. Participants were required to be licensed healthcare professionals with at least one year of clinical experience currently practicing in a hospital. Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous.

A structured questionnaire was developed based on current clinical guidelines and relevant literature related to nutritional assessment and support. The questionnaire included a combination of multiple-choice and open-ended questions and was divided into several sections:

- Demographics and Professional Background: Age, gender, specialty, years of experience, type of healthcare facility, and previous training in nutritional support.
- Knowledge of Nutritional Assessment Tools: Awareness and utilization of screening tools, including MUST, NRS-2002, and SGA.
- Clinical Practice and Attitudes: Frequency and perceived importance of nutritional assessment, involvement in nutrition therapy planning, and collaboration with other disciplines.
- Barriers and Educational Needs: Reported challenges to providing adequate nutritional support, as well as interest in further training.

The finalized questionnaire was hosted on an online survey platform (Google Forms), and the link was distributed through targeted communication channels. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

The study involved 59 healthcare professionals specializing in different fields. 72.9% of them were anesthesiologists, 20.3% were surgeons, and 6.8% were gastroenterologists.

Most respondents (30.5%) reported having between 6 and 10 years of clinical practice. Additionally, 23.5% have more than 20 years of experience, 16.9% have less than 5 years, 15.5% have between 11 and 15 years, and 13.6% possess 16 to 20 years of experience. A total of 83.1% of specialists work in Tertiary Clinical Centers, while 16.9% are employed in secondary hospital centers. Only 8.6% of specialists use the Malnutrition Screening Tools regularly, and the majority of medical professionals work in tertiary care hospitals. The most commonly used screening tools in clinical practice are the Nutritional Risk Screening 2002 (55.9%) and the Mini Nutritional Assessment (23.5%) (Chart 1).

Chart 1. Most commonly used nutritional screening tools

In our facilities, perioperative nutritional support is mainly performed by anesthesiologists (40.7%). Only 12.1% of respondents are performing regular Nutritional support for patients with IBD. The most commonly used tools for nutritional assessment include anamnesis, physical examination, anthropometric measurements, and laboratory tests.

44.1% of respondents are uncertain about how long preoperative nutritional support should last, while 27.1% indicated it should be fewer than 4 days, and 22% suggested a duration of 4 to 7 days before surgery.

Only 12.1% of respondents regularly provide nutritional support for patients with IBD, while

32% do so occasionally, 21% rarely, 20% are unsure how often it is done, and 15% indicated that they do not provide it at all (Chart 2).

Chart 2. Response percentage for regular nutritional support performance in malnourished patients with inflammatory bowel disease.

In the preoperative period, 91% of nutritional support consists of a combination of enteral and parenteral nutrition, whereas 4.5% relies solely on either enteral or parenteral support. Additionally, 21.1% of patients consume liquid carbohydrates orally before surgery.

All respondents acknowledged that the primary challenges include a lack of knowledge, organizational support, time constraints, and available resources.

Discussion

Nutritional support is integral to the multidisciplinary management of IBD. The collaboration of various medical specialists is essential to ensure comprehensive and individualized care for patients with IBD. Each specialty contributes distinct expertise to address the intricate nutritional requirements associated with this disease [23]. Gastroenterologists should play a central role in diagnosing and managing IBD. They are crucial in assessing disease activity, evaluating the nutritional effects of inflammation, and making decisions regarding enteral or parenteral nutrition [24]. In contrast to our study, gastroenterologists expressed the least interest in managing patients during the perioperative period. Unfortunately, in our study, only 8.6% of specialists regularly use Malnutrition Screening Tools for patients with IBD, and the majority of

medical professionals are based in tertiary care hospitals. What is reasonable to consider is that most of these patients are followed at these level medical centers. Surgical specialists, particularly colorectal surgeons, become critical in cases where surgical intervention is required due to complications such as strictures, fistulas, or refractory disease. Surgeons often rely on nutritional assessments to determine timing and readiness for surgery and collaborate with anesthesiologists and gastroenterologists to implement perioperative dietary strategies [25]. As suggested in some studies, our results indicate that the most commonly used screening tools were NRS 2002 and MNR. Other scores were also utilized, but they were used less frequently [16, 17, 19, 20, 26]. There are limited research papers that examine the specific roles of various healthcare specialists in providing perioperative nutritional support to patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). In our facilities, anesthesiologists are primarily responsible for this support, accounting for 40.7% of the role. However, this responsibility is often shared with surgeons and dietitians. Unfortunately, the role of dietitians in our healthcare system is not well-defined [27, 28]. The duration of total parenteral nutrition can vary based on individual patient needs and the severity of their malnutrition or active Crohn's disease. Some studies suggest that administering TPN for 18 to 90 days before surgery, particularly for patients with moderate to severe Crohn's disease, may lead to improved clinical outcomes and a reduction in postoperative complications. On the other hand, some studies suggest that oral intake may be more effective. Considering these various factors, it is not surprising that 44.1% of our respondents are unsure how long nutritional therapy for these patients should last [12, 29]. Furthermore, due to the unique challenges each faces, several key factors can complicate oral intake in these patients. Our study indicates that a combination of oral and parenteral nutritional therapy is the most commonly used approach. Just like with medical interventions, implementing dietary therapies necessitates careful consideration and discussion. It is essential for patients to work closely with a

dietitian and to have clear goals and expectations [12, 30].

As shown in other research, all respondents agreed that the main challenges in this field are a lack of knowledge, inadequate organizational support, insufficient time, and limited resources [31].

Conclusion

The management of perioperative nutrition in patients with IBD undergoing surgery is highly inconsistent. The regular use of specific preoperative nutritional support is lacking, and the methods and timing for such support vary significantly. There is a clear need for further efforts in education, implementation, and the identification of clinical needs and benefits related to nutritional support, as it is crucial for patient care.

References

1. Abraham C., Medzhitov R. Interactions between the host innate immune system and microbes in inflammatory bowel disease. *Gastroenterology*. 2011;140(6): 1729–37
2. Romberg-Camps MJ, Dagnelie PC, Kester AD, Hesselink-van de Kruijs MA, Cilissen M, Engels LG, et al. Influence of phenotype at diagnosis and of other potential prognostic factors on the course of inflammatory bowel disease. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2009; 104:371–83.
3. Ng SC, Shi HY, Hamidi N, Underwood FE, Tang W, Benchimol EI, et al. Worldwide incidence and prevalence of inflammatory bowel disease in the 21st century: a systematic review of population-based studies. *Lancet*. 2017;390(10114):2769–78.
4. Tsai L, Ma C, Dulai PS, Prokop LJ, Eisenstein S, Ramamoorthy SL, et al. Contemporary Risk of Surgery in Patients with Ulcerative Colitis and Crohn's Disease: A Meta-Analysis of Population-Based Cohorts. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2021;19(10):3031–45
5. Fiorindi C, Cuffaro F, Piemonte G, Cricchio M, Addasi R, Dragoni G, et al. Effect of long-lasting nutritional prehabilitation on postoperative outcome in elective surgery for IBD. *Clin Nutrition*. 2021; 40(3):928–35.
6. Mijač D, Janković GL, Jorga J, Krstić MN. Nutritional status in patients with active inflammatory bowel disease: prevalence of malnutrition and methods for routine nutritional assessment. *Eur J Intern Med*. 2010;21(4):315–19.
7. Yamamoto T, Nakahigashi M, Saniabadi AR. Review article: diet and inflammatory bowel disease—epidemiology and treatment. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther*. 2009;30:99–112

8. Hartman C, Eliakim R, Shamir R. Nutritional status and nutritional therapy in inflammatory bowel diseases. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2009;15:2570–8.
9. Balestrieri P, Ribolsi M, Guarino MPL, Emerenziani S, Altomare A, Cicala M. Nutritional Aspects in Inflammatory Bowel Diseases. *Nutrients.* 2020;12(12):372.
10. Grass F, Pache B, Martin D, Hahnloser D, Demartines N, Hübner M. Preoperative nutritional conditioning of Crohn's patients-systematic review of current evidence and practice. *Nutrients.* 2017;9(6):562.
11. Okita Y, Araki T, Okugawa Y, Kondo S, Fujikawa H, Hiro J, et al. The prognostic nutritional index for post-operative infectious complications in patients with ulcerative colitis undergoing proctectomy with ileal pouch-anal anastomosis following subtotal colectomy. *J Anus Rectum Colon.* 2019;3:91-7.
12. Bischoff, Stephan C. et al. ESPEN guideline on Clinical Nutrition in Inflammatory Bowel Disease. *Clin Nutr.* 2023;42(3):352-7.
13. Schwartz E. Perioperative parenteral nutrition in adults with inflammatory bowel disease: a review of the literature. *Nutrition in Clinical Practice.* 2016; 31(2):159–70.
14. Wagner I. J., Rombeau J. L. Nutritional support of surgical patients with inflammatory bowel disease. *Surgical Clinics of North America.* 2011;91(4):787–803
15. Spinelli A., Allocca M., Jovani M., Danese S. Review article: optimal preparation for surgery in Crohn's disease. *Alimentary Pharmacology & Therapeutics.* 2014;40(9):1009–22.
16. Sandhu A, Mosli M, Yan B, Gregor, J, Chande N, Ponich, T et al. Self-Screening for malnutrition risk in outpatient inflammatory bowel disease patients using the malnutrition universal screening tool (MUST). *J. Parenter. Enter. Nutr.* 2016;40:507–10.
17. Kondrup, J.; Rasmussen HH Hamberg, O.; Stanga, Z.; An ad hoc ESPEN Working Group. Nutritional risk screening (NRS 2002): A new method based on an analysis of controlled clinical trials. *Clin. Nutr.* 2003, 22, 321–36.
18. Schiesser, M.; Müller, S.; Kirchhoff, P.; Breitenstein, S.; Schäfer, M.; Clavien, P.-A. Assessment of a novel screening score for nutritional risk in predicting complications in gastro-intestinal surgery. *Clin. Nutr.* 2008, 27, 565–70.
19. Bamba S, Sasaki M, Takaoka A, Takahashi K, Imaeda H, Nishida A, et al. Sarcopenia is a predictive factor for intestinal resection in admitted patients with Crohn's disease. *PLoS ONE* 2017, 12, e0180036.
20. Ulíbarri JI, González-Madroño A, de Villar NG, González P, González B, Mancha A, et al. CONUT: A tool for controlling nutritional status. First validation in a hospital population. *Nutr. Hosp.* 2005;20:38–45.
21. Sood A, Ahuja V, Kedia S, Midha V, Mahajan R, Mehta V, et al. Diet and inflammatory bowel disease: The Asian Working Group guidelines. *Indian J Gastroenterol.* 2019;38:220–46.
22. Bischoff SC, Escher J, Hébuterne X, Kłęk S, Krznaric Z, Schneider S, et al. ESPEN practical guideline: Clinical Nutrition in inflammatory bowel disease. *Clin Nutr.* 2020;39:632–53.
23. Istratescu D, Preda CM, Manuc T, Meianu C, Stroeie T, Diculescu M. A Comprehensive Review of Dietary Approaches in Maintaining Remission of Inflammatory Bowel Diseases in Adults. *Medicina.* 2024;60(7): 1068.
24. Gomollón F, Dignass A, Annese V, Tilg H, Van Assche G, et al. 3rd European evidence-based consensus on the diagnosis and management of Crohn's disease. *J Crohns Colitis.* 2016;11(1):3-25.
25. Walters TD, Griffiths AM, Shaoul R. Nutrition in pediatric inflammatory bowel disease: From etiology to treatment. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2020;17 (10):662–76.
26. Sokulmez P, Demirbağ, AE, Arslan P, Dişibeyaz S. Effects of enteral nutritional support on malnourished patients with inflammatory bowel disease by subjective global assessment. *Turk. J. Gastroenterol.* 2014; 25:493–507.
27. Kim DH, Seo JM, Choi MG. Perioperative nutritional practices and attitudes among gastrointestinal oncologic surgeons in Korea: a nation-wide survey study. *Ann Clin Nutr Metab.* 2023;15(3):81-7.
28. Drover JW, Cahill NE, Kutsogiannis J, Pagliarello G, Wischmeyer P, Wang M, et al. Nutrition therapy for the critically ill surgical patient: we need to do better! *JPEN J Parenter Enteral Nutr* 2010;34:644-52.
29. Di Caro S, Fragkos KC, Keetarut K, et al. Enteral Nutrition in Adult Crohn's Disease: Toward a Paradigm Shift. *Nutrients.* 2019;11(9):2222.
30. Reznikov EA, Suskind DL. Current Nutritional Therapies in Inflammatory Bowel Disease: Improving Clinical Remission Rates and Sustainability of Long-Term Dietary Therapies. *Nutrients.* 2023;15(3):668.

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